

quantiAGREMI

D6: Paper to be submitted to a peer-review journal on parameterisation improvement of model-based bottom-up (up-scaling) GHG emissions and nitrogen loss from soils due to i) bias reduction by consideration of animal housing N deposition and ii) uncertainty reduction through N₂O source partitioning by field-deployable spectroscopic techniques on N₂O isotopic species.

Lead participant for the deliverable: KIT

Due date of the deliverable:

October 31st, 2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable:

December 11th, 2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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Beyond livestock buildings:

Model bias and uncertainty reduction using improved knowledge of ammonia deposition and isotopic composition for simulated N₂O emissions

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Abstract: Process-based models provide an avenue to assess greenhouse gas emissions on scales where measurements alone are impractical. However, outcomes obtained from models are also subject to sources of error, which include model parameter uncertainty, model input uncertainty and model bias. For process-based models, the high-dimensional parameter spaces lead to large uncertainty contributions arising from model parameterization. Additionally, lack of knowledge around ammonia deposition is a known source of model input bias in the estimation of N₂O emissions. Here, using the models LandscapeDNDC and SIMONE, we show how time series measurements of intramolecular N₂O isotopic composition, i.e., site preference (SP), can be used to constrain model parameter uncertainty associated to simulated N₂O fluxes at daily resolution, and can be used as a tool to identify model biases within process-based models. We then investigate the impact of NH₃ deposition on N₂O emissions by simulating a Dutch dairy farm on which ammonia concentrations were recently measured with spatial in addition to temporal resolution. Our results show that including N₂O isotopic composition into a calibration-uncertainty estimation framework significantly reduces parameter uncertainty by on average 64% and that parameter uncertainty is one order of magnitude larger than model bias due to neglect of ammonia deposition in modeling input. However, the relative importance of parameter uncertainty and input bias are site-specific and may differ for stronger source strengths or farms with fertilizer application that is more closely aligned with plant N demand.

Funding: The project 21GRD10 quantiAGREMI has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Background on N₂O emissions modeling

- Current human activities have a significant impact on biogeochemical cycles, with agricultural soils being a major contributor to ongoing nitrogen pollution.
- Tackling this requires estimates of the magnitude and sources of pollution, which are compiled at the regional scale by emissions inventories.
- The Tier 3 approach to determine emissions inventories relies on process-based biogeochemical modeling of environmental processes and coupled nutrient cycles, such as carbon, nitrogen and water.
- Process-based models are necessarily heavily parameterized by quantities which most often cannot be directly measured or quantified. Specification of such parameters constitutes a major source of model uncertainty. Systematic error also arises if relevant underlying processes are not captured by the model, or if key input information is missing or misrepresented.
- Reduction of systematic inaccuracies/uncertainties of model inputs and constraining model parameter uncertainties are therefore both key activities required to improve emissions inventories.
- The objectives of this study are therefore to determine:
 1. If isotopic composition of N₂O fluxes, which contains additional information regarding producing and consuming processes, can be used to constrain model parameter uncertainty.
 2. If ammonia deposition onto surrounding fields can carry a significant impact on N₂O emissions.

1.2 Method highlights

- We use the biogeochemical model LandscapeDNDC, which supports simulation of arable land, grassland and forests.
- To determine the potential added value of isotopic composition measurements on constraining model parameter uncertainties, we simulate two Swiss grasslands and one arable site with available isotopic composition measurements and perform N-isotope tracing simulations using the offline model SIMONE. We perform an uncertainty assessment both with and without the inclusion of isotopic composition measurements to showcase the uncertainty reduction.
- To assess the impact of ammonia deposition on N₂O emissions, we simulate fields on a Dutch dairy farm adjacent to a barn, extracting estimates of deposition ranges from an extensive ammonia sampling dataset measured as part of the quantiAgremi project.

1.3 Key results and conclusions

- In this study, we are able to reduce model parameter uncertainty by on average 64% through inclusion of site preference measurements. This indicates isotopic composition is a valuable marker to further constrain models designed to capture emissions, and should be measured in addition to bulk flux rates where resources permit.
- Ammonia deposition has an impact on N₂O emissions that is at least linear with increasing N-input; however the study site presents a relatively low ratio of N input to the soil from deposition relative to fertilizer application, and the simulated increase of 0.05 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ on the field adjacent to the barn is well within model parameter uncertainty. As such it is recommended that further studies be carried out at locations with stronger source strengths relative to the background ammonia concentration, and with lower fertilizer application rates.

2 Introduction

Nitrous oxide (N_2O) is a potent greenhouse gas (GHG) with a global warming potential 273 times that of CO_2 over a 100 years period and contributes approx. 6% to the total effective radiative forcing of the well mixed GHG (Forster et al. (2021)). In addition to its role as a driver of global warming, N_2O is the single most-important substance in the context of stratospheric ozone depletion (Ravishankara et al. (2009)).

Agriculture is the largest anthropogenic source of N_2O (Ciais et al. (2013)) with the widespread application of synthetic fertilizers and manure on cropland and pasture stimulating microbial nitrogen (N) turnover in soils, eventually leading to increased N_2O production and emission. The global population growth and the associated increasing demand for food and fiber promotes agricultural intensification which - in a business-as-usual scenario - suggests a doubling of N_2O emissions by 2050 (Davidson and Kanter (2014)). Consequently, there is an urgent need for the development of mitigation strategies, which are usually based on field studies. However, quantification of N_2O source strength using field measurements is intense in cost and labor, so that not all soil types and climates can be covered. Simultaneously, climate change alters temperature and soil moisture regimes in ways that either amplify or suppress microbial N_2O production and consumption processes as well as plant production, adding an additional long-term dimension to mitigation research further complicating the situation.

Thus, direct measurements of N_2O emissions at sufficient temporal and spatial scale are unfeasible with current infrastructure and technology. For this reason, notable effort was spent on the development of process-based biogeochemical simulation models during the last decades. Such models use information on soil properties (e.g., bulk density, texture or soil organic carbon), meteorologic information (e.g., radiation, precipitation, temperature) and agricultural management activities (e.g., tilling, planting, fertilization) to calculate soil environmental conditions (e.g., soil moisture and soil temperature), plant growth, and the coupled soil carbon and nitrogen cycles, including relevant N_2O -producing and consuming microbial processes on temporal scales of days to months (Bell et al. (2012); Chirinda et al. (2010); Grosso et al. (2006); Gabrielle et al. (2006); Li (2000); Haas et al. (2013)).

While first applications were proof-of-concept studies at site scale, increasing availability of GIS databases holding spatially explicit model input variables has fostered utilization of biogeochemical models to simulate fluxes at landscape and regional scale (Grosso et al. (2006); Werner et al. (2007); Zaehle et al. (2005); Sifounakis et al. (2024)). This development is especially relevant as so far, national bottom-up N_2O emission inventories are predominately based on Tier 1 or Tier 2 approaches that relate activity data (e.g., fertilizer amount), with an emission factor, to obtain annual N_2O emissions. However, these approaches represent annual total emissions neglecting spatial and temporal variability of fluxes due to soil properties, soil environmental conditions, meteorology, and agricultural management (e.g., timing of fertilizer application). This limitation can be overcome by the presented process-based biogeochemical models, with model-based inventories of soil-derived GHG emissions being defined by the IPCC as Tier 3 method for national GHG reporting. Tier 3 methods are not widely adopted for national inventory reporting of N_2O emissions (one exception being the USA where the process model DayCent is applied) but some countries are moving toward this capability. However, for any simulation study to be admissible, the uncertainties of simulation results need to be included (IPCC (2006)).

Uncertainty of simulation results can be attributed to four sources: (i) model inputs, i.e., information used to initialize and drive the model such as meteorologic information, soil properties and agricultural management (Vrugt et al. (2008)), (ii) model parameters, for instance the rate constants for microbial processes, for instance ammonification of soil organic matter (Vrugt et al. (2003)), (iii) model structure, i.e., inadequate modeling of relevant processes (Refsgaard et al. (2006)) and (iv) accuracy of measurements based on which models were developed and calibrated such as soil-atmosphere greenhouse gas exchange (Van Oijen et al. (2005)). So far, published work on modeling the soil-atmosphere exchange of trace gases has predominately focused on the assessment of input uncertainty (Li et al. (2004); Winiwarter and Rypdal (2001); Werner et al. (2007)). The reason for that is that in many cases the way the model is programmed prohibits the determination of uncertainty due to model structure and that the computational demand of complex models is high (Ogle et al. (2010)). This specifically applies to process-based biogeochemical models as they are highly parameterized, with the range

of plausible parameter values constituting a major source of model uncertainty. However, studies investigating the magnitude of both input and parameter uncertainty have remained scarce due to the high computational demand.

To quantify and reduce parameter uncertainty for highly parameterized, complex models, Bayesian calibration techniques are a powerful tool and were further developed over the past decades (Van Oijen et al. (2005)). The underlying idea (Bayes and Price (1763)) of these techniques is that the probability density function for a given modeled quantity based on an a priori parameter range can be transformed into another, better constrained, density function of model results by means of observations (measurements). In the process, the likelihood that the modeled quantity is within the measurement uncertainty is calculated (Houska et al. (2017); Sifounakis et al. (2024)). By accepting only a subset of modeled quantities with a higher likelihood (Bayesian calibration), the posterior parameter distribution underlying the accepted modeled quantity is better constrained, which leads to reduced parameter uncertainty in a situation in which the quantity in question is calculated using the constrained parameter distributions.

As this involves a large number of model runs, Monte Carlo methods have been developed for conducting Bayesian calibration and subsequent determination of parameter uncertainty. Most prominent methods are the Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo approach (MCMC)—specifically the Metropolis-Hastings, MH, Algorithm (Metropolis et al. (1953); Hastings (1970))—and the sampling importance resampling (SIR) approach (Rubin (1988)). The MH algorithm is an iterative process randomly selecting a new candidate parameter vector in each step. The candidate vector is accepted or rejected based on the likelihood compared to the measurements and a new candidate vector is selected based on the accepted parameter vector. This is repeated for a large number of iterations, with the accepted parameter vectors representing a better constrained subset of model parameters. To prevent the random walk from getting stuck in a local minimum, multiple chains are used to assess convergence of the posterior parameter distributions. In contrast, the SIR method is non-iterative. To obtain a better-constrained parameter set, a large number of modeled quantities arising from the a priori parameter distributions are obtained, and those with a higher likelihood compared to the measurements are selected with sample probability proportional to their importance weights (Gurung et al. (2020)).

Obviously, it is desirable to consider the full parameter set for deriving parameter uncertainty. Simultaneously, the amount of model runs necessary to derive a robust estimate of the posterior parameter distribution directly scales with the amount of parameters investigated. Process-based models often use more than hundred uncertain parameters, making an uncertainty estimate using the full parameter set impractical. Additionally, not each parameter affects the modeled quantity in the same way, so that only a fraction of model parameters may need to be considered and other parameters can be considered fixed with minimal error relative to the considered output (McAllister et al. (1994)). To identify the most relevant parameters, a global sensitivity analysis (GSA) that identifies the most influential parameters is recommended to significantly reduce the computational demand required for estimates of model uncertainty (Saltelli et al. (2007)). As sensitivity analyses, such as the Sobol or Morris screening (Morris (1991); Sobol (2001); Saltelli et al. (2007)) also require a large number of model runs, GSA and the SIR methods can be used in a complementary way as both the parameter sensitivities and the likelihoods of a modeled quantity within measurement uncertainty can be calculated from the same model output.

In the specific case of modeling N_2O emissions, one aspect further complicates reduction of parameter uncertainty. N_2O can be produced and consumed by several processes, with N_2O being a by-product of nitrification, the conversion of ammonium (NH_4^+) to nitrate (NO_3^-) and an obligate intermediate of denitrification. Denitrification is the stepwise reduction of NO_3^- to nitrite (NO_2^-), nitric oxide (NO), N_2O and finally di-nitrogen (N_2), so that the terminal step of denitrification consumes N_2O . For this reason, the soil-atmosphere exchange of N_2O that is usually used for calibration and likelihood calculation represents the net emission; however the relative contribution of the different production and consumption processes remains unconstrained through the flux measurements as they cannot discriminate between the relative contributions of nitrification and denitrification. Advances in research on N_2O isotopic composition revealed that the isotopic composition gives additional information on the processes responsible for the soil N_2O emission. In particular, the isotopic quantity site preference, SP, which is a measure for the relative frequency of ^{15}N substitution on the terminal or

central N atom of the linear N-N-O molecule, is a powerful tool for source process partitioning (Toyoda and Yoshida (1999); Denk et al. (2017)). While measurements of SP were only possible through flask sampling and subsequent laboratory analysis on a mass spectrometer for a decade, the advent of laser spectrometers has enabled in-situ measurements of N₂O isotopic composition in unprecedented daily temporal resolution (Mohn et al. (2012); Wolf et al. (2015); Ibraim et al. (2019, 2020)).

In view of the above explained aspects, improving model results through reduction of input and parameter uncertainty requires better identification of systematic biases, improved input datasets and a broader database of observations providing additional process information. One possible systematic bias concerns the fate of NH₃ that is released from animal housings (or adjacent manure storage facilities). While some part of released NH₃ is deposited in the vicinity of the barn, the remaining NH₃ can react with acidic gases such as H₂SO₄ or HNO₃ to form secondary aerosols (Aaman et al. (1998); Sutton et al. (1998); Erisman and Schaap (2004)). These secondary aerosols, for instance (NH₄)₂SO₄ or NH₄NO₃, are suspended in the air and can, thus, be transported by the wind over long distances before being eventually deposited dry or wet (Sutton et al. (1998)). Only few studies assessing NH₃ deposition around hot-spots of NH₃ emission like farms with manure storage facilities or livestock housings are available (Shen et al. (2016)). The available studies suggest an exponential decay of deposition around farms, with deposition rates ranging from 42 to 614 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ within 50m distance to 5 to 104 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ within 270 to 1000 m distance (Fowler et al. (1998); Walker et al. (2008); Hao et al. (2009); Shen et al. (2016)). The huge variability is due to different lengths of the measurement periods, the share of the periods during which the measurement instrument was exposed to the downwind NH₃ plume of the farm as well as the number of animals kept on the farm. Farm footprint averages range between 5 and 145 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ within 10 to 1000 m (Fowler et al. (1998); Walker et al. (2008); Hao et al. (2009); Shen et al. (2016)). The deposition of NH₃ to (semi-) natural ecosystems can lead to biodiversity loss, soil acidification and eutrophication (Bergström and Jansson (2006); Bouwman et al. (2002); Stevens et al. (2004); Cowan et al. (2022)). However, animal housings are frequently surrounded by agricultural areas so that NH₃ deposited to agricultural fields can lead to total N loads exceeding crop fertilizer demand at times of fertilizer application. While N addition in general stimulates soil N cycling and plant growth, excess N load non-linearly increases N₂O emissions (van Groenigen et al. (2010)). Since there is a significant research gap with regard to the amount and spatial extent of N deposition in the vicinity of animal housings, neglect of this additional N source may lead to bias in model-supported, bottom-up N₂O inventories.

Additionally, datasets which provide information on the relative contributions of different N₂O producing processes have become available that can be used to additionally constrain model parameters for specific processes with large potential to reduce parameter uncertainty (Mohn et al. (2012); Wolf et al. (2015); Ibraim et al. (2020)).

For this reason, the objectives of this study are to (i) develop a calibration-parameter uncertainty analysis framework capable of incorporating N₂O isotopic composition measurements, (ii) assess the potential to reduce parameter uncertainty by additionally considering N₂O isotopic composition, (iii) determine the effect of N deposition in the vicinity of a livestock housing on modeled N₂O emission and (iv) relate model bias to parameter uncertainty. To this end, we used the biogeochemical model LandscapeDNDC (Haas et al. (2013)) in conjunction with the stable isotope model for nutrient cycles SIMONE (Denk et al. (2019)) for a series of grassland and agricultural sites located in Switzerland and the Netherlands for which N₂O isotopic composition datasets or near-field NH₃ deposition is available.

3 Methods

To accomplish the aims of this study, a novel calibration and uncertainty analysis framework was developed. This is capable of considering measurements of N isotopic composition in addition to common N₂O flux measurements, as detailed in section 3.1. Subsequently, the framework was deployed on three Swiss sites for which measurements of N₂O fluxes and N₂O isotopic composition are available and which were simulated using LandscapeDNDC and SIMONE. To assess how the impact of deposition on emissions compares with model

Figure 1: Schematic flowchart showing the key steps that we use to arrive at estimates of model parameter uncertainty.

parameter uncertainty, we then developed a protocol to estimate the increase in N_2O emissions with increasing N-input due to deposition surrounding a Dutch dairy farm, described in section 3.2.

3.1 Estimating model parameter uncertainty

As part of the QuantiAgremi project, a novel calibration and uncertainty analysis framework has been developed for the models LandscapeDNDC and SIMONE. This framework combines field measurements carried out at different sites (section 3.1.1), the associated results of the biogeochemical model LandscapeDNDC and the corresponding N-isotope tracing simulations, obtained offline using the SIMONE model (Denk et al. (2019)). This framework is schematically represented in Fig. 1. In brief, most influential parameters of LandscapeDNDC for N_2O emissions are identified by means of a global sensitivity analysis (GSA, see section 3.1.2). Subsequently, parameters are calibrated using measurements and likelihood estimation (section 3.1.3) which leads to a posterior distribution of parameter vectors. The posterior distributions are used to estimate the model parameter uncertainty based on a Monte Carlo resampling approach (section 3.1.4). The calibration-uncertainty estimation was carried out in two stages: following the left branch in Fig. 1, we evaluate a reference model uncertainty which makes use of N_2O flux measurements alone; second we apply a combined scheme involving both branches simultaneously to determine the model parameter uncertainty, taking both the N_2O flux measurements and isotopic composition measurements into account. While SIMONE calculates the isotopic composition of all N-compounds that appear in LandscapeDNDC, not all isotopic quantities are equally suitable for the reduction of model uncertainty. Some isotopic quantities, such as soil $\delta^{15}N$, represent N cycling over long time periods, i.e., decades, or—for instance NH_4^+ —are extremely difficult to simulate accurately as they cannot be determined in high temporal resolution and depend on the isotopic composition of different precursor materials. For this reason, the quantity site preference, SP (Eq. 1), was included in this study as it can be measured in daily to sub-daily temporal resolution, is independent of the precursor compounds and provides information on the relative contribution of different N_2O producing microbial processes (Toyoda et al. (2002); Sutka et al. (2006); Heil et al. (2014)).

$$SP = \delta^{15}N^\alpha - \delta^{15}N^\beta . \quad (1)$$

Table 1: Soil properties for the three isotope study sites Chamau, Beromünster and Zürich averaged to depth increments of 0 to 10, 10 to 30, 30 to 60 and 60 to 90 cm.

depth [cm]	Chamau					Beromünster					Zürich				
	ρ_d [g cm ⁻³]	C [%]	N [%]	clay [%]	pH [-]	ρ_d [g cm ⁻³]	C [%]	N [%]	clay [%]	pH [-]	ρ_d [g cm ⁻³]	C [%]	N [%]	clay [%]	pH [-]
0-10	0.93	4.23	0.45	19.0	5.3	1.30	3.54	0.59	24.6	5.5	1.39	1.24	0.16	20.0	7.3
10-30	1.32	1.83	0.22	21.9	5.3	1.40	1.78	0.22	22.9	5.3	1.36	1.23	0.16	20.0	7.3
30-60	1.53	0.61	0.88	20.1	5.4	1.47	0.67	0.10	26.4	5.5	1.33	1.00	0.13	20.0	7.3
60-90	1.57	0.35	0.05	9.9	5.5	-	-	-	-	-	1.33	0.90	0.11	20.0	7.3

SP distinguishes whether the heavy N-isotope is primarily located in the central (α -configuration) or terminal site (β -configuration) of the linear N-N-O molecule. Since different processes respectively favour one or other configuration with different rates, this can be used to extract statistical information regarding the origin of an ensemble of produced N₂O molecules. Formation of the α -configuration is favoured by nitrification processes (SP \sim 32 %), while denitrification and nitrifier-denitrification do not show a preference for either configuration (SP \sim 0 %), as discussed by [Denk et al. \(2017\)](#).

Consequently, SP has the capacity to impose additional constraints on the flux rates of N₂O calculated by the biogeochemical model LandscapeDNDC. These additional constraints are derived from insights into the relative contributions of nitrification and denitrification, which are recognised as the processes responsible for producing N₂O. The need for the off-line model SIMONE is due to the fact that most biogeochemical models, including LandscapeDNDC, are incapable of calculating N isotopic composition. To calculate N-compound isotopic composition, SIMONE uses the Rayleigh equations of isotopic distillation ([Mariotti et al. \(1981\)](#)). While one central quantity of the aforementioned approach is the residual fraction of the substrate, the other is the isotope effect, i.e., the constant that describes the difference in reactivity between the light and heavy isotope. The residual fraction is provided by LandscapeDNDC's soilchemistry module METRX to SIMONE, and the isotope effects originate from literature resources. In this manner, LandscapeDNDC and SIMONE are utilised in unison to model the dynamics of N-isotopic composition in biogeochemical nitrogen cycling ([Denk et al. \(2019, 2017\)](#)).

To assess the potential to reduce parameter uncertainty by additionally considering N₂O isotopic composition, specifically SP, we applied our framework to three Swiss sites (section 3.1.1) with available time series measurements of both N₂O emissions and site preference. As data coverage for the site Chamau was highest, in addition to the individual site-based calibrations, we selected Chamau as a reference site and used its post-calibration average parameter vector to run validation simulations for the other two sites. Our aim with this was to verify if the average parameter vector from one grassland site (e.g. Chamau) would be 1) representative of another, sometimes grazed, grassland site (e.g. Beromünster), and 2) unsuitable for use on arable sites (e.g. Zürich) due to large differences in initial site conditions, such as soil carbon and N content. All results are collected and described further in section 4.1.

3.1.1 Sites used in this study

The site at Chamau is an intensively managed grassland at an elevation of 398m, with anoxic gleysol with a soil organic carbon content of 4.23% (Tab. 1), for which N₂O fluxes and corresponding isotopic composition measurements are available at daily resolution from a summer campaign running from June to September 2013 ([Wolf et al. \(2015\)](#)).

The site at Beromünster is a grassland site used as pasture at the top of a hill at 797m, characterized by silty soil and a soil organic carbon content of 3.54% (Tab. 1; [Ibraim et al. \(2020\)](#)). Daily measurements of N₂O flux and isotopic composition were carried out between August and December 2017.

In contrast, the site close to Zürich is an arable site managed by Agroscope in Switzerland and is operated with mixed-management strategies to serve ongoing projects. Its dominant soil type is cambisol ([Keel et al. \(2019\)](#)). A measurement campaign was carried out by EMPA over the summer of 2024, measuring N₂O fluxes

a) One iteration of full sensitivity ranking of internal soilchemistry parameters. b) Sensitivity ranking of nitrification and denitrification parameters for N gas emissions.

Figure 2: Results of Global Sensitivity analyses on soilchemistry module METRX within the LandscapeDNDC model. **a)** Ranking of sensitivity indices with respect to N₂O emissions from one of several sampling runs. Almost all model variability can be accounted for by less than half of the examined set, with the top 10 parameters accounting for the largest share of variability. **b)** Comparison of sensitivities to nitrification and denitrification parameters reveals structure in the LandscapeDNDC's sensitivity to N-cycling. We identify two groups with distinct parameter type: the first group, boxed in blue, contain parameters corresponding to internal model effects which influence nitrification and denitrification. The second group, boxed in red, correspond to parameters that describe how nitrification and denitrification respond to environmental factors such as soil PH or temperature. The first group is more influential than the second on modeled N-gas emissions under ordinary environmental conditions.

and isotopic composition on weekly temporal scale for four different treatments respectively: two control fields of sugar beet and winter barley without fertilizers applied, and two fields with sugar beet and winter barley with NPK fertilizers applied. Of the four treatments, site preference data was scarce for all except the sugar beet with NPK treatment, so in this investigation our calibration-uncertainty framework was applied exclusively to this treatment.

3.1.2 Global sensitivity analysis

Though it is desirable to consider the full parameter set for deriving parameter uncertainty, the amount of model runs necessary scales exponentially with the amount of parameters investigated. For this reason, it is good and common practice to reduce the full parameter set by identifying the most influential parameters for the quantity in question, here N₂O emission. To this end, a global sensitivity analysis was carried out over a comprehensive list of 127 parameters which govern nitrification, denitrification, decomposition, microbial dynamics, soil properties and diffusion within the soilchemistry module METRX. In the process, SALib libraries for Sobol sampling and sensitivity analysis were applied over the corresponding high dimensional space spanned by LandscapeDNDC results (Sobol (2001); Saltelli (2002); Saltelli et al. (2010); Herman and Usher (2017); Iwanaga et al. (2022)). Multiple iterations with over 10⁶ simulation runs were sampled in order to confirm convergence of the ranking of most influential parameters on N₂O emissions. The ranking of the top 50 parameters converged, from which the largest share of variability of simulated N₂O emissions originates from the top 10

parameters, as exemplified in Fig. 2, panel a).

The first iteration of sensitivity analyses revealed two highly correlated and influential parameters, both involved in the evaluation of the simulated anaerobic soil volume fraction, referred to here in short as ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 . The anaerobic volume fraction, *anvf*, is calculated in the model as

$$\text{anvf} = e^{-(\phi_2 * p_{O_2})^{\phi_1}}, \quad (2)$$

where p_{O_2} is the oxygen partial pressure. It is clear from this relationship that values of the parameters ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 must be selected in a correlated way to ensure physically meaningful anaerobic volume fractions at a given oxygen partial pressure. In particular, under standard atmospheric conditions, where p_{O_2} is approximately 21%, we assume that the anaerobic volume fraction does not exceed 20% at higher oxygen partial pressures, and discard parameter pairs which do not fall in this range. In addition, we must remove parameter pairs for which the exponential decay is so strong that anaerobicity dominates completely at low partial pressures.

Informed by multiple sensitivity analyses, and to accommodate computational resource limitations, we selected in total a set of 17 parameters to investigate in this study, including the above mentioned *anvf* parameters, a comprehensive list of which appears in Table 3.

3.1.3 Calibration by likelihood estimation

The global sensitivity analysis described in the previous section led to a list of 17 selected model parameters. The values of these 17 parameters were sampled from a uniform distribution over the allowed ranges in the model. In total, 2^{14} parameter vectors were sampled as model inputs and these were used to run 2^{14} LandscapeDNDC and SIMONE model iterations for each site. Then statistics regarding the plausibility of parameter vectors are subsequently obtained by estimating the likelihood of a given parameter vector occurring, combined with the knowledge of the prior distributions from which the vectors were sampled which in this case are all uniform.

To do this, we consider that the measurement data D used for calibration is normally distributed with standard deviation σ , such that the likelihood L of a model result Y corresponding to a parameter vector $\vec{\theta}_j$ for a single statistically independent event at timestep t_i is given by

$$L(D|\vec{\theta}_j) = e^{-\left(\frac{Y(t_i, \vec{\theta}_j) - D(t_i)}{\sigma}\right)^2}, \quad (3)$$

The probability associated to a parameter vector $\vec{\theta}_j$ can be evaluated as

$$p(\vec{\theta}_j|D) \propto L(D|\vec{\theta}_j)p(\vec{\theta}_j), \quad (4)$$

with the knowledge that $p(\vec{\theta}_j)$ is constant for all j .

We calculate the probability distribution over all sampled parameter vectors for each simulation timestep corresponding to an available measurement event. In the case of N_2O measurements, we make an additional distinction between peak and background, and aggregate all measurements above the background corresponding to a single peak into one event. This allows us to make the assumption that all events i considered are in fact independent and that therefore the log-probabilities are additive. This in turn allows us to construct the probability distribution corresponding to a set of N events with parameter vectors $\vec{\theta}$ as

$$p = p_0 e^{-\sum_{i=0}^N \left(\frac{Y_{N_2O}(\vec{\theta}, t_i) - D_{N_2O}(\vec{\theta}, t_i)}{\sigma}\right)^2}, \quad (5)$$

where p_0 is a normalization constant. The resulting probability distribution is then used to assess the reference uncertainty of modeled N_2O emissions arising from model parameterizations that have not yet been constrained by the use of isotope simulations, further discussed in section 3.1.4. In this investigation, we additionally assess the utility of isotopic composition as a tool to constrain modeled N_2O , such that knowledge of the plausible

parameter sets for site preference is also of value. A corresponding likelihood and probability distribution for site preference is similarly evaluated for the given parameter vector in terms of the available measurement events for site preference. In this case, all measurement events M are directly assumed to be independent, with corresponding probability distribution

$$p = p_0 e^{-\sum_{i=0}^M \left(\frac{Y_{SP}(\vec{\theta}, t_i) - D_{SP}(\vec{\theta}, t_i)}{\sigma} \right)^2} \quad (6)$$

This probability distribution can be used in combination with that for N_2O to arrive at a multivariable distribution for the plausible parameter vectors constrained by both N_2O and site preference

$$p = p_0 e^{-\lambda_1 \sum_{i=0}^M \left(\frac{Y_{SP}(\vec{\theta}, t_i) - D_{SP}(\vec{\theta}, t_i)}{\sigma} \right)^2 - \lambda_2 \sum_{i=0}^N \left(\frac{Y_{N_2O}(\vec{\theta}, t_i) - D_{N_2O}(\vec{\theta}, t_i)}{\sigma} \right)^2} \quad (7)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 can be used to apply a relative weighting to the respective calibration variables. For this study, we work with $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2$. With this framework in place to assess the probability distributions associated to the sampled parameter vectors, an estimate of the model parameter uncertainty can next be evaluated.

3.1.4 Assessment of model parameter uncertainty, and model validation

To obtain an estimate of model parameter uncertainty, we perform an importance resampling of simulation outputs according to the probability distributions obtained following calibration (SIR, section 2). We resample 1000 parameter vectors weighted by the corresponding probability based on the likelihood of each vector, and then extract the mean and standard deviation on the corresponding daily simulation outputs for N_2O and site preference. We use this procedure to obtain estimates of model parameter uncertainties, shown in Figs. 4 - 8 and discussed in section 4.1. Individual site-based calibrations were carried out for the grasslands Chamau and Beromünster and the arable Zürich based site.

We selected Chamau as the reference site for additional analyses, due to both the larger magnitude of emissions peaks observed during the campaign window and the high frequency of measurements. With a selected reference site, we first direct our investigation to the assessment of how well a parameter vector representative of the mean calibrated simulation performs when validated on additional grassland sites, and to showcase that grassland calibrations are not expected to work with arable sites. For this study, we use Beromünster as an additional grassland site for validation, and the arable Zürich site to demonstrate the need for independent calibration data on grassland and arable sites. Since the statistical mean of the simulation outputs does not correspond to the direct result of any one simulation with a well-defined parameter vector, we construct a representative parameter vector by averaging over the importance sampled parameter vectors and validate the new mean parameter vector against the three sites. The results are shown in Fig.9, and discussed in section 4.1. A comprehensive assessment of the distances between parameter vectors for arable and grassland sites—and which respective parts of the parameter space are favoured by each—was beyond the scope of this project, requiring more data from arable sites, and will be the focus of future work.

3.2 LandscapeDNDC simulation and measurements of the Dutch Dairy farm

To assess the potential impact of ammonia deposition originating from livestock housings on agricultural N_2O emissions, our investigation focused on simulating a field used for agriculture directly adjacent to the barn of a Dutch Dairy farm. The field is 121m wide and extends over approx. 750m away from the barn, with the area of the field amounting to close to 9 ha. The soil is a medium textured loam with a sand and clay content of 30 and 25%, respectively. In the top 10 cm, carbon content, nitrogen content, bulk density and pH amount to 1.8%, 0.2%, 1.12 g cm^{-3} and 7.3, respectively. The crops cultivated on this farm follow a rotation typical of the area comprising maize, potatoes and grass, for which yield levels are available for years 2010-2018. As yields were high for this site, a derogation regarding fertilizer application rates allows high N inputs, which were up to 400

Figure 3: Ammonia concentrations and estimated deposition rates averaged and fit over 5 of the 6 campaign periods. Measurements from period 1 were not included due to additional contributions to ammonia concentrations of manure application on a section of the farm.

kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ for maize and grass, while approx. 80 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ were usually applied to potatoes. The fertilizer used on this farm has been a mix of slurry and mineral fertilizer.

The presented farm was the location of a recent joint experimental campaign of QuantiAGREMI partners. One outcome of the measurement campaign was a dataset spanning six weeks of alpha sampler measurements of the ammonia concentration at different locations surrounding the livestock housing on the dairy farm. Samplers were exchanged and analysed approximately weekly to determine average NH₃ concentration from which an estimate of the radial profile of deposited ammonia could be obtained as detailed below. Specifically, we use the ammonia concentration measurements averaged over the duration of weeks 2 through 6 of the campaign. The measurements from the first week were not included in the average used here, as in that time a large amount of ammonia was detected by the alpha samplers on the Northern border of the farm. This has been attributed to the application of fertilizer on a Northern field, and has not been included to avoid overestimation of deposition from sources unrelated to the presence of the housing. Wind direction data was measured at high frequency during the campaign and all wind directions were representatively observed. As such, we make a simplifying assumption that the distribution of the ammonia plume from the livestock housing is purely radial in order to estimate its impact at a fixed distance from the housing, as will be further discussed in Section 4.2.

The averaged measured concentrations n_{NH_3} were therefore fit with least squared error as a radial function of distance from the housing, as shown in the top panel of Fig. 3. A daily dry deposition rate was then estimated by assuming a constant deposition velocity v_d , and the corresponding deposition rate can be estimated as follows

$$d_{NH_3} = v_d n_{NH_3} . \quad (8)$$

The result of this estimation is shown in the bottom panel of Fig. 3, for which we assume a representative deposition rate of $v_d = 0.0107 \frac{m}{s}$ on the dairy farm. Considering the standard deviation of the measurements, these deposition rates translate into an additional deposition of 16 to 29 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ at 20 m distance from the barn and 6 to 9 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ at a distance of approx. 750 m distance from the barn.

To assess the effect of N deposition due to the barn, LandscapeDNDC simulations of the Dutch dairy farm were run for a total of 30 different input values of deposition ranging from 6 to 29 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹, covering the range of measured deposition with distance from the housing. The simulations were set up using the aforementioned soil and typical management data for the farm obtained by colleagues at WUR, and local climate data from the e-obs database (Cornes et al. (2018)). Deposition of aerosols from rainfall was not considered. In addition, different N management scenarios were simulated for the described field directly adjacent to the barn. The first scenario is the reference scenario without additional N deposition. The second scenario reduces the N fertilizer application within the first 100 meters by the amount equivalent to the N deposition due to the barn within the named area. The third scenario redistributes this N to the rest of the field.

As presented in the introduction, agricultural inputs or deposition in general stimulate soil N cycling and plant growth. Through the fundamental processes of isotopic fractionation and mixing, such stimulation affects soil δ¹⁵N, with a series of studies showing that larger N input results in higher ¹⁵N enrichment in soils Robinson (2001); Högberg and Johannisson (1993); Kriszan et al. (2009, 2014); Skadell et al. (2025), due in part to the tendency for the lightweight ¹⁴N isotope to be volatilized more readily in soils with high emissions. In order to support the interpretation of the modeling study and assess the effect of deposition on distance from the barn, soil samples were taken in transects arranged along the main and crosswind directions, ranging from the barn to the field borders.

4 Results

Figure 4: Chamau site, calibration and uncertainty results for **a)** reference and **b)** isotope cases.

	Chamau	Beromünster	Zürich
Reference calibration N ₂ O emissions [kg N ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹]	4.29±1.99	1.43±1.32	0.38±0.33
Isotope calibration N ₂ O emissions [kg N ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹]	3.79 ±0.22	1.22 ±0.29	1.57±0.25
Percentage uncertainty reduction on N ₂ O emissions	88.9%	78.0%	25.6 %

Table 2: Summary of annual N₂O emissions per site following the two calibration schemes.

In this section we present results relating to the two main objectives of this study: first, the impact of including isotopic composition on the assessment of model parameter uncertainty, with respective results collected in Figs. 4-9 and Tables 2 and 3, discussed in the next section 4.1; second, a study of the impact of ammonia deposition originating from livestock housings on N₂O emissions, with relevant results collected in Fig. 10-11, and further described in section 4.2.

4.1 Model parameter uncertainty

By calibrating the model using flux measurements, and resampling from the respective distribution of parameter vectors for each site, we arrive at a confidence interval on the parameter sets which led to plausible flux outputs. The range of outputs spanned by this set gives us a first reference-estimate of model parameter uncertainty. A refined uncertainty estimate is subsequently obtained by a second calibration on both flux and isotopic composition measurements, followed by resampling. This was carried out for each of the three measurement sites with available measurements of N₂O isotopic composition. The results for Chamau are collected in Fig. 4, and showcase a visible reduction in the size of the error bars for simulated flux with the inclusion of isotopic composition in the calibration strategy, as will be discussed in section 5.1. The difference in the uncertainty estimates between the reference and isotopic calibration and resampling strategies for all sites is summarized in Tab. 2.

The respective results for the calibration performed on the site at Beromünster are found in Fig.5.

The measurement techniques applied to the site in Zürich led to different measurement frequency, with corresponding measurements corresponding to an average over the preceding seven days. This led to a sparser measurement dataset, with a larger potential for the calibration results to be impacted by individual outlier measurements and for the model to become incorrectly constrained. To test the sensitivity of the calibration strategy to variability in a sparse dataset and look for drivers of possible model bias, we carried out two additional calibrations in which selected features in the measurements that LandscapeDNDC could not simulate were removed: first, emissions measurements not clearly associated to management or rewetting events and that were also not present in the control treatment dataset were removed from the calibration; second, the measurement corresponding to the lowest measured site preference value was additionally removed. The results of the corresponding calibration and uncertainty assessments are found in Figs. 6-8.

To understand how different the calibrated parameter sets for each site are with respect to the default, we evaluated the average parameter vectors obtained from both reference and isotopic calibrations. We used these values to examine the distance between the calibrated and default parameter vectors, by considering their difference from the default vector component-wise, as collated in Tab. 3.

Finally, the site at Chamau was chosen as a reference site for further investigation of the response of other sites to a parameter vector obtained by taking the average of all parameter sets resampled from the distribution calibrated with isotopic composition, in order to assess the applicability of the calibration to other grassland sites, and to verify that grassland calibrations do not work well on arable sites. These results are presented in Fig. 9.

Figure 5: Beromünster site, calibration and uncertainty results for **a)** reference and **b)** isotope cases.

Figure 6: Zürich site, calibration and uncertainty results for **a)** reference and **b)** isotope cases.

Figure 7: Zürich site, excluding measured emissions not associated to fertilizer or rewetting events.

Figure 8: Zürich site, additionally excluding the negative site preference measurement.

(1) Validation of average parameter vector from Chamau, on the site Chamau.

(2) Validation of average parameter vector from Chamau, applied to the Beromünster site.

(3) Validation of average parameter vector from Chamau, applied to the Zürich site.

Figure 9: Validation of the average of calibration sample of parameter vectors from the Chamau calibration, applied to the three test sites.

Parameter	Chamau		Beromünster		Zürich	
	% change ref. calib.	% change iso. calib.	% change ref. calib.	% change iso. calib.	% change ref. calib.	% change iso. calib.
AMAX	146.6	191.7	59.3	-81.2	62.5	-46.2
D_EFF_REDUCTION	715.5	823.4	420.9	551.1	369.5	228.9
F_DECOMP_T_EXP_1	-37.2	-46.7	-23.0	-71.5	-12.9	-70.2
F_DECOMP_CLAY_2	-35.9	-82.2	3.2	63.5	16.6	29.6
F_DENIT_N2_1	-19.4	-12.4	-29.6	24.5	-19.9	27.0
F_DENIT_N2_2	-58.0	-74.9	-41.1	-8.3	-31.0	-54.7
F_DENIT_NO	-2.9	24.2	-28.9	20.9	-38.7	-67.9
F_NIT_FRAC_MIC	66.9	48.7	39.1	140.1	38.4	14.8
MUEMAX_C_MIC	22.3	14.5	1.2	22.1	-18.5	65.7
MUEMAX_C_DENIT	142.3	-23.5	1128.2	415.8	760.0	1077.5
KR_DC_HUM2	-21.2	-65.6	29.8	-78.1	0.8	101.6
KR_DC_HUM3	236.3	281.0	146.5	295.0	69.7	-64.2
KMM_N_DENIT	237.8	277.5	165.1	159.1	172.3	251.7
KMM_NH4_NIT	376.8	238.4	467.5	55.7	433.4	115.4
KMM_O2_NIT	302.5	147.0	395.8	281.5	411.4	555.9
F_SANVF_1	28.3	-27.6	36.8	58.7	39.1	70.6
F_SANVF_2	131.5	179.8	116.6	178.3	119.9	171.4
Total change (absolute magnitude)	2581.5%	2559.0%	3132.4%	2505.4%	2614.5%	3013.3%
Denit. parameter change	460.4%	412.6%	1392.8%	628.5%	1021.9%	1478.9%
Nit. parameter change	746.2%	434.1%	902.4%	477.4%	883.2%	686.1
Denit. contribution to total change	17.8%	16.1%	44.5%	25.1%	39.1%	49.1%
Nit. contribution to total change	28.9%	17.0%	28.8%	19.1%	33.7%	22.8%

Table 3: Response of individual parameters to the two calibration schemes on each of the studied sites. Denitrification and nitrification related parameters are labeled in blue and red respectively. The reference calibrations, based on N₂O flux measurements alone, favour greater alterations to nitrification parameters than those complemented by isotopic composition.

4.2 Systematic input bias: effect of deposition on modeled N₂O emissions

Panel a) of Fig. 10 shows that modeled N₂O emissions increase linearly with additional NH₄⁺ deposition. At the closest location to the barn, simulated emissions increase by 18%, whereas the increase is less than 1% at approx. 750 m from the barn. Though the model reacts linearly on N deposition, N₂O emissions decrease exponentially with distance from the barn, corresponding to the deposition decreasing exponentially with distance (Fig. 3). Panel b) of Fig. 10 shows the N₂O as function of distance from the barn for the four management scenarios "No housing", "Housing", "Reduction" and "Reduction and Redistribution". Within the first 100 meters of the field directly adjacent to the farm, these N₂O emission rates amount to 3.33, 3.82, 3.71 and also 3.71 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ for these four scenarios, respectively 4. This corresponds to distinct increases within the first 100 meters when taking into account the presence of a barn (15, 11 and 11%, respectively for scenarios "Housing", "Reduction" and "Reduction and Redistribution"); however across the whole area of the field, the emissions increased only by 1.5, 1.2 and 1.2% for the same scenarios.

Table 4: N₂O emissions and change for different N management scenarios.

Scenario	N ₂ O 0-100m [kg N ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹]	N ₂ O whole field [kg N ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹]	change [%]	change whole field [%]
No housing	3.33	3.33	-	-
Housing	3.82	3.38	15	1.5
Reduction in first 100 m	3.71	3.37	11	1.2
Reduction and redistribution	3.71	3.37	11	1.2

Figure 10: Response curves of modeled N₂O to increasing deposition. **a)** Response of simulated N₂O to linear increase in deposition over the range expected in the Dutch dairy farm case study. **b)** Simulated response of N₂O to deposition as a function of radial distance from the barn, and additional response curves for modeled N₂O to the two additionally considered mitigation scenarios.

As described in section 3.2, soil measurements were carried out on the Dutch dairy farm in the summer of 2024 to determine the soil $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ content and establish if the impact of N deposition from the presence of the livestock housing was distinguishable above other sources of N input to the soil. In contrast to the expected decline in soil $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ with distance from the barn, Fig. 11 shows that there was no clear pattern in soil $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ as function of distance from the barn.

Figure 11: Results of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ soil sampling along two orthogonal transects, main and cross wind, distributed with distance from the barn. High values of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ are observed at all distances from the barn, consistent with long term effects of high input of fertilizer and manure throughout the farm. The share of ammonia deposition relative to the annual nitrogen input to the soil is low, and the soil content is roughly constant along the transects with distance from the barn.

5 Discussion

5.1 Model parameter uncertainty

The calibration and uncertainty analysis framework developed in this work was applied to simulations of the sites at Chamau, Beromünster and Zürich respectively.

In the case of Chamau, after both the reference and isotope calibrations, the simulated emissions show a much stronger response to management and rewetting events, and perform better than the default parameterization when compared to the observations, see Fig. 4. The uncertainty associated to the simulated peak emissions is visibly decreased from the reference to the isotopic calibration scheme. This showcases the potential value of isotopic composition measurements of N_2O fluxes, specifically site preference, as a tool to help constrain model parameter uncertainty. In addition, the site preference results reveal a strong model bias towards nitrification in the second half of July that persists following the calibration. This was the driest part of the measured period (Wolf et al. (2015)). Following the rewetting event at the end of July, LandscapeDNDC is slow to respond (if at all) with a recovery of nitrification processes. This additionally showcases the potential for isotopic measurements to identify systematic model biases. Addressing the source of this bias will be the subject of future work.

For the site at Beromünster, systematic difficulties to model soilwater content prior to rewetting led to poor simulated emissions responses to the rewetting event seen at the beginning of the measurement campaign, see Fig. 12. This could not be addressed with calibration of the model to the parameters considered in this study, with only 158 of the 2^{14} sampled parameter vectors showing any simulated emissions above the background following the rewetting. Several of these parameterizations additionally display spurious emissions and were penalized against. This site will therefore be the subject of future investigation of model bias relating to soil water content. Despite this difficulty, the calibration was successful in penalizing parameterizations that lead

to spurious emissions and in producing a more smooth and faithful representation of site preference compared to the default. This was the case even for the reference calibration, in which relative to the default, the simulated range of site preferences mostly captures the measurements within uncertainty, albeit with the mean underestimating site preference. For the calibration including site preference, the performance is noticeably improved, and the corresponding uncertainty ranges on both N₂O emissions and site preference are reduced, due to the decreased weighting associated to parameter vectors which can simulate the N₂O comparably but not simultaneously site preference.

The measurement campaign at the site near Zürich yielded weekly average data for N₂O emissions and site preference for four different treatments from which we simulated the field with sugar beet and applied NPK fertilizers. For this dataset, a total of seven data points was available for the calibration of site preference. The reference calibration on N₂O performed relatively well (see Fig. 6), succeeding in reducing a spurious simulated emissions peak originally observed around mid-September in the default simulation, and bringing the order of magnitude of the post-fertilizer peaks better in line with the measurements. However, within the measured dataset there are several additional peaks which occurred throughout mid-June and July that could not be captured by the model. It is unknown what the main driver of these measured emissions was. The measurements on the corresponding control field observed background level emissions during the same period, and thus these emissions measured on the NPK field could be related in a non-trivial way to the prior fertilizer treatments, or unidentified measurement errors. No modeled process within LandscapeDNDC can to our knowledge capture such delayed emissions following fertilizer application, and it is therefore consistent that no model parameterization was capable of reproducing these features. To verify if the presence of these data points had any impact on the calibration process, we additionally investigated if a calibration disregarding these points would lead to any significant difference in the result (see Fig. 7). No significant difference was observed. Due to the scarcity of site preference measurements, the calibration strategy including site preference led to less plausible N₂O simulation results in both the previously discussed cases, with an artificially raised background baseline. To determine what the driver of this behaviour could be, we repeated the calibration excluding the lowest site preference measurement to reduce the amount of forcing towards lower simulated site preference values (see Fig. 8). This led to a reduction in the raised baseline relative to the previous two cases, and provides a clue that forcing the model to low site preference values on this site leads to an overestimation of the simulated N₂O background emissions. However, due to the lack of available site preference measurements, no conclusion can be confidently drawn regarding whether the default model overestimates the share of nitrification to denitrification ongoing in the soil. This emphasizes that datasets with coarse temporal resolution may erroneously affect calibrations, especially through inflation of baseline emissions and that data quality assessment and control of the novel measurement techniques around SP may need further development.

For all three sites, we do observe that the inclusion of site preference as a second calibration variable leads to a significant reduction in the model parameter uncertainties by on average 64%, as summarized in Tab. 2.

To quantify the amount that the calibration process changes the distribution of parameter values with respect to their default values, we compress the information contained in the distribution of resampled parameter vectors into a single representative average parameter vector. An example validation that such average parameter vectors are representative of the calibrated simulation output can be seen in Fig. 9 panel (1). In addition, we sought to test whether the calibration for one grassland site would be robust enough to hold on the other grassland site. Given the differences in soil carbon and N content between long term arable and grassland sites (Gachibu Wangari et al. (2024)), it is not expected that the calibration for a grassland site would work on an arable site, but was nonetheless investigated here. We selected Chamau as the reference site, in light of the higher density of measurements and high magnitude peaks that favoured the most successful calibration. We calculated the average parameter vector for Chamau and used this as the input parameter vector for the Beromünster and Zürich sites, respectively in panels (2) and (3) of Fig. 9. In the case of applying the average parameter vector from Chamau to Beromünster, the N₂O emissions are marginally improved across the measured time series if we exclude the systematic failure to capture the rewetting peak. The simulated site preference also shows improvement, capturing much more faithfully the structure of the site preference measurements, albeit underestimating the absolute value across the time series. This suggests that a successful calibration on a grassland site can be

Figure 12: Default LandscapeDNDC results at daily scale tracking N_2O emissions and soilwater content. A noticeable discrepancy in simulated soilwater content is present prior to the start of available measurements and just prior to the rewetting event.

reasonably applied to the simulation of other grassland sites. On the other hand, when applying the average parameter vector from Chamau to the arable Zürich based site, we find that the baseline N_2O emissions are no longer correctly represented. Specifically in this case, using the average calibration vector from Chamau reduces the modeled nitrification and significantly lowers the baseline for modeled site preference. This supports the conclusion that distinct parameterizations are indeed required for arable and grassland sites.

We evaluated the average parameter vectors for each of the calibrated sites and characterized their deviation from the default vector component-wise. We then calculated the percentage change of each component of the calibrated average parameter vector with respect to the default, the results of which are collected in Tab. 3. From the list of calibration parameters, five have direct control on denitrification processes and three on nitrification. To represent the share of the changes attributable to denitrification and nitrification parameters respectively, we tally the absolute magnitude of the percentage changes to all individual parameters and calculate what share of this corresponds to changes in denitrification and nitrification parameters. These shares are shown in the bottom two rows of the table. The calibrations using isotopic composition show a clear reduction in the amount that nitrification related parameters are adjusted relative to the default. This is consistent with the fact that the nitrification parameters are strong drivers of N_2O flux emissions and that without the additional information supplied by isotopic calibration, nitrification parameterizations that achieve the right results for wrong reasons can be favoured. Hence isotopic composition measurements assist in constraining model nitrification parameterizations.

5.2 Effect of deposition on modeled N_2O emissions

The NH_3 deposition rate measured at the Dutch site ranged between 29 and 6 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{a}^{-1}$ at distances from the barn of 20m and approx. 750m respectively. This is lower, but comparable, to deposition rates observed for a poultry farm located in Scotland (Fowler et al. (1998)) where 42 and 5 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{a}^{-1}$ were measured at a distance of 15 and 270 m from the barn. Higher deposition rates were reported for a swine production facility in North Carolina (Walker et al. (2008)) for which deposition rates of 145 to 16 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{a}^{-1}$ were reported at 10 and 500 m distance from the barn and a beef cattle feedlot in Canada, where 104 and 49 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{a}^{-1}$ were measured at a distance of 0 and 700 m from the barn (Hao et al. (2009)). Highest deposition rates of 614 to 104 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{a}^{-1}$ were determined for a cattle feedlot in Australia (Shen et al. (2016)), but the distinctly higher rates result from higher temporal resolution of the measurements and a large share of the sampler exposition to

the downwind plume of the feedlot. Spatiotemporal averaging of the flux rates to an area in 1000 m distance to the feedlot resulted in an overall deposition of $67.5 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$. Consequently, literature deposition rates for cattle feedlots were much higher than in our study of a dairy cattle livestock housing. This difference is partly due to the difference in livestock number (180 in this study, and 17500 and 22500 for [Shen et al. \(2016\)](#); [Hao et al. \(2009\)](#), respectively) and the lower atmospheric NH_3 concentrations in the vicinity of the farms.

For the reference scenario based on soil, weather and management information of the site, the annual N_2O emissions calculated by the biogeochemical model LandscapeDNDC amounted to $3.33 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$. N_2O emissions are—among other factors—stimulated by fertilizer input. A compilation of approx. 20 studies on N_2O emissions from maize cropping in a recent global modeling study ([Xu et al. \(2020\)](#)) reported N_2O emissions ranging between close to 0 and $5 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ for synthetic fertilizer application rates between 0 and $450 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$. On our site, $400 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ were applied as a combination of synthetic fertilizer and manure. By contrast, in the global study, emissions for sites receiving 291, 350 and $450 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ synthetic fertilizer amounted to 4.21 to $5.13 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$. Thus, the magnitude of simulated emissions in our case is slightly lower than the observations suggest for similar N application rates. This discrepancy may be to some extent due to manure containing approx. 50% organic N, which is not immediately available for N_2O producing processes like nitrification and denitrification, so that the simulated N_2O emissions generally agree with observations.

The LandscapeDNDC simulations showed a linear increase in N_2O emissions from 3.33 to $3.95 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ for an addition of approx. 25 kg N ha^{-1} compared to the approx. 400 kg N ha^{-1} fertilization of the site. In other words, the additional 25 kg N ha^{-1} deposition caused $0.6 \text{ kg N}_2\text{O}$ emissions (18%), equivalent to an emission factor of 2.4%, whereas the average emission factor for the fertilization of $400 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ is much lower and amounts to 0.8%. While the latter value is close to the IPCC emission factor for fertilizers ([IPCC \(2006\)](#)), the large discrepancy between the emission factors indicates that modeled N_2O emissions non-linearly scale with N input considering a range of 0 to $430 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$. Such non-linear response has been observed in a study summarizing 19 studies on N_2O emissions from croplands ([van Groenigen et al. \(2010\)](#)), and for a more recent study on total denitrification losses from agricultural systems ([Takeda et al. \(2023\)](#)). Especially the study by [van Groenigen et al. \(2010\)](#) showed that this non-linearity is associated with N surplus, i.e., the difference between fertilizer N applied and N taken up by aboveground biomass. Aboveground biomass N has been shown to linearly increase with fertilizer application rate for application rates up to 210 kg N ha^{-1} ([Tripathi et al. \(2025\)](#)) or 300 kg N ha^{-1} ([van Groenigen et al. \(2010\)](#)). However, the latter study showed an offset of 100 kg N ha^{-1} and a slope of 0.51, so that surplus N is applied starting from an application rate of about 200 kg N ha^{-1} . In addition, [Zou et al. \(2024\)](#) showed that aboveground N leveled off at 150 kg N ha^{-1} or even decreased at a rate of 187 kg N ha^{-1} , confirming that surplus N can be expected for an application rate of around 200 kg N ha^{-1} . In view of the considerable N surplus expected for our site, the effect of additional N deposition can be considered large compared to agricultural systems in which crop N demand and fertilizer N application rate are more closely coupled. This is especially relevant for evaluating the effect of N deposition on N_2O emission on the studied site. While the increase of emissions for moderate deposition of 25 kg N ha^{-1} is rather large, the area receiving the highest load is rather small, as the deposition rates decline exponentially with distance from the barn. For this reason, the N_2O emissions increase only by 15% for the first 100 m of the field studied, but for the whole field, emissions only increase by 1.5%. Thus, the effect of N deposition in our case was small, in the range of 0.04 to $0.05 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ compared to a model uncertainty of 0.2 to $2 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ (Tab. 2). However, the overall effect ultimately depends on the deposition rate, the rate of N inputs from management, and size of the fields or the spatial density of other livestock facilities. Thus, additional research including stronger point sources such as the feedlots of [Hao et al. \(2009\)](#); [Shen et al. \(2016\)](#), farms without derogated management, and landscapes with smaller field sizes are pertinent.

The soil $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ measurements made at the Dutch farm, shown in Fig. 11, show clearly elevated concentration of the heavy ^{15}N isotope over the whole field adjacent to the barn. This is consistent with large annual N input from organic fertilizers ([Robinson \(2001\)](#); [Högberg and Johannisson \(1993\)](#); [Kriszan et al. \(2009, 2014\)](#); [Skadell et al. \(2025\)](#)). No structure was observed reflecting the decay of N input from deposition with distance from the barn. Given that the share of N deposition from the total N input for the year 2024 on the sampled fields

was low (estimated at most $29 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ compared to the fertilizer input of around $400 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$, corresponding to roughly 7% of total input), and fertilizer inputs were consistently high on the farm dating back at least as far as 2010 while the livestock numbers remained relatively constant, we conclude that on sites with a low ratio of N input from deposition to fertilizer, soil $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ measurements cannot be used as a proxy for ammonia deposition originating from livestock housings. However, further study is required on sites with lower background ammonia emissions and crop demand N adjusted application rates, for which it is expected that a signature of the ammonia deposition profile should be observable.

6 Conclusions

In this study we have shown using the models LandscapeDNDC and SIMONE that measurements of N_2O isotopic composition, specifically site preference, are a useful tool for constraining model parameterizations relevant to N_2O emissions, and reducing corresponding model uncertainties. Concretely, inclusion of high frequency time series of site preference measurements in model calibration allows distinction between parameterizations which produce plausible emissions rates, but exhibit the wrong underlying balance between denitrification and nitrification processes. In addition, discrepancies in modelled site preference that are unresolvable by varying model parameterizations serve as indicators of potential model biases, and provide an insightful window onto systematic sources of error within process-based models.

On this basis, inclusion of isotopic composition and site preference in the design of future measurement campaigns is recommended, where resources permit, to expand the available measurement database and facilitate improving process-based models beyond the site scale. Data is required for both arable and grassland sites independently to allow for maximum potential to improve modeling efforts.

Generalization of the calibration and uncertainty analysis framework developed in this study to a multi-site scheme was beyond the scope of this investigation, and would be of future value.

Annual N deposition estimates were included in our simulations of the Dutch dairy farm as a function of distance from the barn, derived from data measured over the summer of 2024. This site has a derogation allowing higher than usual fertilizer application rates, and as such, the share of N input to the field originating from ammonia deposition is relatively small (ranging from 1% at 750m to 7% at 20m of total N inputs). The increase in simulated N_2O emissions attributed to the presence of the barn triggered a linear response in emissions, but the moderate increase in N input of ~ 25 compared to the overall N input of $\sim 400 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ resulted in an over-proportional emission increase of 18%. This indicates that the model represents the often reported non-linear response of N_2O emissions N addition exceeding plant N uptake, but that the sensitive turning point of the N-emissions vs. N input function had been exceeded for this site. In addition, given that ammonia deposition represents such a small share of the total input to the field, the model bias incurred by not including the presence of the livestock housing (underestimation of emissions by order $0.05 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$) is well within our current estimates of model parameter uncertainty (ranging between 0.2 to $2 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$). These numbers are highly site specific, and further study is required on sites with fertilizer application rates that are more closely aligned with crop N demand, with stronger source strengths such as larger feedlots, and different distribution and density of fields surrounding the livestock housing.

The soil $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ content measured at the Dutch dairy farm reveals high heavy ^{15}N isotope concentrations that are largely flat with distance from the barn. There is no discernible decay in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ within uncertainty that could serve as a proxy for ammonia deposition. This is likely due to the small share of the ammonia deposition from the total N input. As such, future proxy studies should focus on farms with stronger source strengths and/or without derogated management.

Acknowledgements

We thank Christof Ammann and Sonja Keel from Agroscope for providing data on the Zürich site. We thank Andrew Smerald, David Kraus and Edwin Haas for helpful discussions on LandscapeDNDC parameterization

and calibration and uncertainty assessment. We acknowledge the E-OBS dataset from the EU-FP6 project UERRA (<http://www.uerra.eu>) and the Copernicus Climate Change Service, and the data providers in the ECA&D project (<https://www.ecad.eu>)".

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